

Quadratic Relations and Oblong Parabolic Prime Sieve: A New Approach to Goldbach's Conjecture

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Abstract: This study expands the geometric tool known as the [Parabolic Sieve of Primes \(PSO\)](#) [12] by introducing the Oblong Parabolic Sieve of Primes with Offset (Oblong PSO). This technique, applying an offset to the oblong D-parabola instead of the square D-parabola, facilitates the isolation of primes in the Cartesian plane. We demonstrated that principles applicable to square numbers can equivalently apply to oblong numbers, resulting in the discovery of the *C003515 Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Center-Aligned Bases of f -Triangles*. To address the limitation of non-vertically aligned primes, we developed the *C003518 Expanded Table*, suggesting consistent vertical prime pairs, thereby supporting Goldbach's Conjecture. The *C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table* further explores prime pairs within quadratic sequences. These findings, combined with the study on [The Quadratic Distribution of Integers Relative to Squares and Oblongs](#) [13], provide robust evidence for Goldbach's Conjecture. This study adopts the terms 'primals' and 'compounds' for clarity and is a continuation of the Mersenne Forum thread [The proof of Goldbach's conjecture and Landau's problem](#), accessible at <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=28200>.

Keywords: Oblong Parabolic Sieve of Primes, Prime Number Identification, Quadratic Relations Prime Pairs, Goldbach's Conjecture, Integer Mapping, Parabolic Patterns, Primal and Compound Numbers.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification: 11A41: Primes, 11B37: Recurrences, 11N05: Distribution of Primes, 11Y55: Calculation of Integer Sequences, 11B83: Special Sequences and Polynomials, 11N13: Primes in Progressions.

*Don't be afraid to 'sheet' your ideas down.
Even if they're not perfect, you can always improve them later.*

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1 Introduction

In this initial study, our aim is to expand upon the geometric tool known as the Parabolic Sieve of Primes (PSO), as elaborated in [Kusniec's Theorem: Demonstrating Prime Numbers Between Squares and the Two Adjacent Oblong Numbers](#) [12], which sieves prime numbers along the number line. Our expansion involves applying an offset to the oblong D-parabola instead of the square D-parabola. This expansion takes place in the Cartesian plane and reproduces, at each offset, all the infinite oblong parabolas studied in [Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors \(MID\) Framework](#) [4].

We have named this new geometric tool the Oblong Parabolic Sieve of Primes with Offset (Oblong PSO). The Oblong PSO is a sieving technique that utilizes a parabolic approach adjusted by an offset to isolate primes, offering a unique method for prime identification.

When studying [The SOM Numbers](#) [2], we demonstrated that everything applicable to square numbers can similarly and equivalently be applied to oblong numbers. In the study [Kusniec's Theorem: Demonstrating Prime Numbers Between Squares and the Two Adjacent Oblong Numbers](#) [12], we used the Parabolic Sieve of Primes with Offset (Oblong PSO) with the parabola of squares. In the present study, we will use the Oblong PSO with the parabola of oblongs, which we will now refer to as Oblong PSO.

Through this expansion, we discovered the C003515 Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Center-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO. This table revealed a limitation in that not all columns contain vertically aligned primes.

To address this limitation, we developed the C003518 Expanded Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Center-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO with Vertical Quadratic and Horizontal Linear Equations. This expanded table suggests that it is always possible to find a pair of vertically aligned primes in every row, thereby supporting Goldbach's Conjecture as a theorem.

To further illustrate this characteristic, we created the C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table. This table provides the sum, difference, and product of all pairs of prime numbers for any even sum or difference between them. By doing so, it offers a detailed examination of the relationships between prime pairs within quadratic sequences.

The objective of this table is to illustrate the consistency and patterns in the formation of prime pairs through quadratic relationships. By analyzing these patterns, we can gain a deeper understanding of the distribution of prime numbers and provide evidence supporting the Goldbach Conjecture. When combined with the findings from the study [The Quadratic Distribution of Integers Relative to Squares and Oblongs](#) [13], this demonstrates that the Goldbach Conjecture can be proven as a theorem. The table highlights the infinite combinations of prime numbers that satisfy specific quadratic relationships, demonstrating the robust nature of these mathematical properties.

In this study, we adopt the terms 'primals' and 'compounds' in place of the more traditional 'primes' and 'composites' as defined in the study [Integers are only Primals and Compounds](#) [5]. This terminology aligns with recent findings on the intrinsic properties of the sieve of primes. Additionally, for any abbreviations or terms used that are not explicitly explained within this text, we recommend consulting [Symbolic Conventions and Lexicon](#) [7]. This resource provides

comprehensive definitions and context to ensure a unified understanding of the terminology employed throughout our analysis.

This study is a continuation of the thread [The proof of Goldbach's conjecture and Landau's problem](https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=28200) on the Mersenne Forum, which can be accessed at <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=28200>.

2 The Oblong Parabolic Sieve of Primes with Offset (Oblong PSO)

In this initial study, we aim to expand upon the geometric tool known as the Parabolic Sieve of Primes (PSO), as elaborated in [Kusniec's Theorem: Demonstrating Prime Numbers Between Squares](#) [12], which sieves prime numbers along the number line. Our expansion involves applying an offset to the oblong D-parabola instead of the square D-parabola. This expansion takes place in the Cartesian plane and reproduces, at each offset, all the infinite oblong parabolas studied in [Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors \(MID\) Framework](#) [4].

We have named this new geometric tool the Oblong Parabolic Sieve of Primes with Offset (Oblong PSO). The Oblong PSO is a sieving technique that utilizes a parabolic approach adjusted by an offset to isolate primes, offering a unique method for prime identification.

The following sections detail the construction of the Oblong PSO.

2.1 Fundamentals of the Oblong PSO Construction

For the construction of the Oblong PSO, we also will use GeoGebra, available at <https://www.geogebra.org/>. To maintain clarity and due to the size of the figure for our didactic purposes, we will demonstrate the construction using images for an offset $f = 4$.

The first step in the Cartesian plane is to mark all odd integers on the X-axis (dark blue points), all odd square numbers (yellow points), all numbers that are odd (square minus 1), which are (even square) minus 1 (orange points), and finally, all oblong numbers, which are the only even numbers we highlight on the X-axis and mark with an "X" in maroon color.

The next step is to plot the Oblong D-parabola in red with an offset f . This parabola has the general equation $x = -y^2 + (2f + 1)y$. By applying the offset formula for quadratics [6], we get $f = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{b}{2a} \right] = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{2f+1}{2(-1)} \right] = \text{roundz}[f + 0.5] = f$.

Thus, we obtain Figure C003511, illustrating the Oblong PSO construction first figure.

Figure 1. C003511 First Illustration of the Oblong PSO Construction with Offset f=4

Next, we add the axis of symmetry of the D-parabola, which has the equation $y = (f + 0.5)$ and is drawn in green with a dash-dot line style. On this axis of symmetry, we mark the points ‘Oblong minus Oblong (ObMn)’. These points have coordinates $(x, y) = ((f^2 + f) - (n^2 - n), (f + 0.5))$, where n is a natural number. These points indicate the X-coordinate positions that generate an even composite result from the difference of two oblongs in the same procedure as we obtain some even composites in [The Quadratic Distribution of Integers Relative to Squares and Oblongs](#) [13] and [Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors \(MID\) Framework](#) [4].

We then mark the odd numbers on the oblong D-parabola in black and the even numbers in red. Each natural number n has a corresponding point on the oblong D-parabola according to the formula $(x, y) = (-h^2 + (2f + 1)h, h)$. Even points h (in red) and the number 1 (in black) are marked with an "X". However, all odd points h greater than 1 are the only ones that can generate odd composites, and these are marked as black points.

At this stage, we obtain the figure C003512 of the Oblong PSO construction:

Figure 2. C003512 Second Illustration of the Oblong PSO Construction with Offset $f=4$

To complete the construction of the Oblong PSO, we draw the lines that cover all SOM numbers [2] on the X-axis. These fundamental lines intersect the two closest consecutive points equidistant from the vertex (symmetry point [6]) of the oblong D-parabola, one on each side of the parabola's axis of symmetry. These lines are named and equated as follows:

InitialSquareMinus1Line: $x - y = f^2 - 1$ (in brown color) is the ascending diagonal line with a 1: 1 inclination that covers the initial (square minus 1) number at the base of the square h-triangle for $h = f + 1$, where the base of the triangle is on the number line (X-axis).

InitialSquareLine: $x - y = f^2$ (in brown color) is the ascending diagonal line with a 1: 1 inclination that covers the initial square number at the base of the square h-triangle for $h = f$, where the base of the triangle is on the number line (X-axis).

FinalSquareMinus1Line: $x - y = (f + 1)^2 - 1 = f^2 + 2f$ (in brown color) is the descending diagonal line with a 1: -1 inclination that covers the final (square minus 1) number at the base of the square h-triangle for $h = f$, where the base of the triangle is on the number line (X-axis).

FinalSquareLine: $x - y = (f + 1)^2 = f^2 + 2f + 1$ (in brown color) is the descending diagonal line with a 1: -1 inclination that covers the final square number at the base of the square h-triangle for $h = f + 1$, where the base of the triangle is on the number line (X-axis).

CentralOblongLine: $x = f^2 + f = (f + 1)^2 - (f + 1)$ (in brown color) is the vertical line that covers the central oblong number at the base of the square h-triangle for $h = f$ and $h = f + 1$, where the base of the triangle is on the number line (X-axis).

Figure 3. C003513 Third Illustration of the Oblong PSO Construction with Offset $f=4$

In our last figure of the construction, we present the Oblong PSO in its final form. First, we highlight the two square h-triangles for $h = f$ and $h = f + 1$, both with a square area.

For each offset, the vertex views the base of the two triangles equally divided by the central oblong number into the two zones Square-to-Oblong (SO) and Oblong-to-Square (OS).

2.2

The functionality of the Oblong PSO mirrors the Square PSO. The parabola here shifts in unitary offset steps following $x = -y^2 + (2f + 1)y$. Consequently, the diagonals of the Oblong PSO continuously adjust their slopes to consistently cover the product of two integers, which are represented by points with integer coordinates on the D-parabola.

Let $N(-n^2 + (2f + 1)n, n)$ and $M(-m^2 + (2f + 1)m, m)$ be two points representing the integers n and m on the D-parabola, as explained in the construction of Figure 2, C003512 above. The line connecting these points is given by the equation $x = nm + (2f + 1 - n - m)y$.

Notice that this line always intersects the X-axis at $x = nm$ when $y = 0$. This implies that regardless of the offset, the line joining points N and M will always cross the X-axis at $x = nm$. This characteristic ensures that the product of the integers n and m is always represented on the X-axis, demonstrating the consistent behavior of the Oblong PSO.

This is why the vertical to the parabola at its two points closest to vertex results in a square number, as in this case $n = f$ and $m = f + 1$, the product is equal to $f^2 + f$.

2.3 Characteristics of the Oblong PSO

The advantage of the Oblong PSO over the Square PSO is that we now have two h-triangles, each with two pairs of lateral sides. One lateral side covers a square number, while the other

covers a square minus one. The benefit of this is that all pairs of squares and square minus one will be covered as composites, with exactly one oblong number separating each SO zone from the OS zone at the base of the triangle with $\frac{f}{2}$ odds each.

Another characteristic that differentiates the Oblong PSO from the Square PSO is that we never have two odd points aligned vertically along the oblong D-parabola. Each vertical line of points with integer coordinates forms an ObMOb, which is always even. The advantage of this is that it becomes more evident that only descending diagonals (excluding verticals) can cover the odd composites in h-triangle, which geometrically shows that we can only consider odd prime divisors greater than 1 and less than f in our analysis as described in [Kusniec's Theorem: Demonstrating Prime Numbers Between Squares](#) [12]. See the figure:

Figure 4. C003514 Third Illustration of the Oblong PSO Construction with Offset f=4

All diagonals that produce odd numbers on the X-axis need to have 1: *odd* inclination. Only these diagonals with odd inclinations can produce odd numbers on the X-axis.

Within each h-triangle where $h = f$ is odd, there can be no odd multiples of f . Thus, as we vary f , the descending and ascending lines alternately cover even and odd numbers.

The base of the h-triangle for $h = f$ contains f [*even*] or f [*odd*] - 1 odd points equally divided on each side of the central oblong.

The area of each square centered at ObMn within the oblong D-parabola is $\frac{2n+1}{2}$.

3 Studying the Distribution Properties of Odd Prime Numbers in the Quadratic Distribution of Integers

To study the properties of the quadratic distribution of integers, specifically odd primes, we will examine how odd integers are distributed along the bases of the infinite f-triangles in the Oblong PSO. For example:

- For $f = 1$, we have only the odd number 1.
- For $f = 2$, we have the odd numbers 3, 5, and 7.
- And so on, leading to the following table:

C003515 Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Left-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO																											
dif	f	f^2	f^2-1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	
	0	0	-1	-1																							
2	1	1	0	1																							
2	2	4	3	3	5	7																					
6	3	9	8	9	11	13																					
6	4	16	15	15	17	19	21	23																			
10	5	25	24	25	27	29	31	33																			
10	6	36	35	35	37	39	41	43	45	47																	
14	7	49	48	49	51	53	55	57	59	61																	
14	8	64	63	63	65	67	69	71	73	75	77	79															
18	9	81	80	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	95	97															
18	10	100	99	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119													
22	11	121	120	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141													
22	12	144	143	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167											
26	13	169	168	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189	191	193											
26	14	196	195	195	197	199	201	203	205	207	209	211	213	215	217	219	221	223									
30	15	225	224	225	227	229	231	233	235	237	239	241	243	245	247	249	251	253									
30	16	256	255	255	257	259	261	263	265	267	269	271	273	275	277	279	281	283	285	287							
34	17	289	288	289	291	293	295	297	299	301	303	305	307	309	311	313	315	317	319	321							
34	18	324	323	323	325	327	329	331	333	335	337	339	341	343	345	347	349	351	353	355	357	359					
38	19	361	360	361	363	365	367	369	371	373	375	377	379	381	383	385	387	389	391	393	395	397					
38	20	400	399	399	401	403	405	407	409	411	413	415	417	419	421	423	425	427	429	431	433	435	437	439			
42	21	441	440	441	443	445	447	449	451	453	455	457	459	461	463	465	467	469	471	473	475	477	479	481			
42	22	484	483	483	485	487	489	491	493	495	497	499	501	503	505	507	509	511	513	515	517	519	521	523	525	527	
46	23	529	528	529	531	533	535	537	539	541	543	545	547	549	551	553	555	557	559	561	563	565	567	569	571	573	

Figure 5. C003515 Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Left-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO

In the C003515 Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Left-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO, the first vertical column alternates between odd perfect squares and odd (square minus 1) numbers, following the sequence <https://oeis.org/A085046>. The difference between terms in one row and the next are even numbers doubled, forming the sequence <https://oeis.org/A168276>.

Nothing prevents us from aligning the elements to the right, resulting in:

C003517 Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Right-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO																				
diff	f	f^2	f^2-1	-23	-22	-21	-20	-19	-18	-17	-16	-15	-14	-13	-12	-11	-10	-9	-8	-7
	0	0	-1																	
2	1	1	0																	-1
6	2	4	3																	3
6	3	9	8																	5
10	4	16	15																	7
10	5	25	24																	9
14	6	36	35																	11
14	7	49	48																	13
18	8	64	63																	15
18	9	81	80																	17
22	10	100	99																	19
22	11	121	120																	21
26	12	144	143																	23
26	13	169	168																	25
30	14	196	195																	27
30	15	225	224																	29
34	16	256	255																	31
34	17	289	288																	33
38	18	324	323																	35
38	19	361	360																	37
42	20	400	399																	39
42	21	441	440																	41
46	22	484	483																	43
46	23	529	528																	45
				485	487	489	491	493	495	497	499	501	503	505	507	509	511	513	515	517
				531	533	535	537	539	541	543	545	547	549	551	553	555	557	559	561	563
				569	571	573														

Figure 6. C003517 Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Right-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO

In this table, the last vertical column follows the sequence <https://oeis.org/A227786>, which also has the difference between terms in one row and the next as even numbers doubled, also forming the sequence <https://oeis.org/A168276>.

These two tables represent the same phenomenon or a mutual complement of sequences with an offset of one unit. This is because:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{https://oeis.org/A227786}[f] + 2 &= \text{https://oeis.org/A085046}[f + 1] \\ \text{https://oeis.org/A227786}[f] &= \text{https://oeis.org/A085046}[f + 1] - 2 \end{aligned}$$

In other words, where the vertical column of C003517 ends, the vertical column of C003515 begins with an offset of one unit.

This possibility of aligning elements on the left or right suggests investigating their alignment in the center. Thus, we obtain the following table:

C003516 Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Center-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO																																																	
diff	f	f^2	f^2-1	-11	-10	-9	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11																							
	0	0	-1												-1																																		
2	1	1	0												1																																		
4	2	4	3												3	5	7																																
6	3	9	8												9	11	13																																
8	4	16	15												15	17	19	21	23																														
10	5	25	24												25	27	29	31	33																														
12	6	36	35												35	37	39	41	43	45	47																												
14	7	49	48												49	51	53	55	57	59	61																												
16	8	64	63												63	65	67	69	71	73	75	77	79																										
18	9	81	80												81	83	85	87	89	91	93	95	97																										
20	10	100	99												99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119																								
22	11	121	120												121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141																								
24	12	144	143												143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167																						
26	13	169	168												169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189	191	193																						
28	14	196	195												195	197	199	201	203	205	207	209	211	213	215	217	219	221	223																				
30	15	225	224												225	227	229	231	233	235	237	239	241	243	245	247	249	251	253																				
32	16	256	255												255	257	259	261	263	265	267	269	271	273	275	277	279	281	283	285	287																		
34	17	289	288												289	291	293	295	297	299	301	303	305	307	309	311	313	315	317	319	321																		
36	18	324	323												323	325	327	329	331	333	335	337	339	341	343	345	347	349	351	353	355	357	359																
38	19	361	360												361	363	365	367	369	371	373	375	377	379	381	383	385	387	389	391	393	395	397																
40	20	400	399												399	401	403	405	407	409	411	413	415	417	419	421	423	425	427	429	431	433	435	437	439														
42	21	441	440												441	443	445	447	449	451	453	455	457	459	461	463	465	467	469	471	473	475	477	479	481														
44	22	484	483	483	485	487	489	491	493	495	497	499	501	503	505	507	509	511	513	515	517	519	521	523	525	527	529	531	533	535	537	539	541	543	545	547	549	551	553	555	557	559	561	563	565	567	569	571	573

Figure 7. C003515 Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Center-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO

Aside from an offset, this would be equivalent to the Kircheri Triangle at <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=28110> without even numbers, filled only with odd numbers. Similarly to the Kircheri triangle filled with non-negative integers, the consecutive vertical differences of elements between rows now cover the entire spectrum of even numbers represented by the sequence <https://oeis.org/A005843>.

Unlike the previous two tables, if we can prove that there is at least one pair of primals aligned vertically between any two consecutive rows, we prove Goldbach's Conjecture. For instance, from offset $f = 0$ to $f = 13$, there is always at least one pair of primals aligned vertically in some column of the table. However, from $f = 13$ to $f = 14$, there is no pair of primals aligned vertically, suggesting that there are no primal pairs whose difference is 28.

Nevertheless, according to the study [The Quadratic Distribution of Integers Relative to Squares and Oblongs](#) [13], we know this is not true. Therefore, to visualize the infinitude of odd numbers on the number line and the infinitude of primal pairs we can obtain in each row, we will expand the vertical quadratic equations, which is also equivalent to expanding the horizontal linear equations. Thus, we obtain:

C003518 Expanded Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Center-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO with Vertical Quadratic and Horizontal Linear Equations																									
1	25	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
42	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129
41	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100	101	102	103	104
40	79	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127
39	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129
38	83	85	87	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131
37	85	87	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133
36	87	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135
35	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137
34	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139
33	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141
32	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143
31	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145
30	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147
29	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149
28	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151
27	105	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153
26	107	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155
25	109	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157
24	111	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159
23	113	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161
22	115	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163
21	117	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165
20	119	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167
19	121	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169
18	123	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171
17	125	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173
16	127	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175
15	129	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177
14	131	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179
13	133	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181
12	135	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183
11	137	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185
10	139	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187
9	141	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189
8	143	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189	191
7	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189	191	193
6	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189	191	193	195
5	149	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189	191	193	195	197
4	151	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189	191	193	195	197	199
3	153	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189	191	193	195	197	199	201
2	155	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189	191	193	195	197	199	201	203
1	157	159	161	163	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	181	183	185	187	189	191	193	195	197	199	201	203	205

Figure 8. C003518 Expanded Table of Odd Integers Distributed Along the Center-Aligned Bases of f-Triangles in the Oblong PSO with Vertical Quadratic and Horizontal Linear Equations <https://1drv.ms/i/s!A7rslv070x3WjkdA7160efkpxL20v20B?e=8VQYBI>

This table is equivalent to expanding the Kircheri Triangle filled with odd numbers in the same manner as we expanded the Kircheri Triangle filled with non-negative integers, as demonstrated in the study on the Mersenne number <https://www.mersenneforum.org/showthread.php?t=28194>. By aligning the bases centrally and applying vertical quadratic and horizontal linear expansions, we achieve a comprehensive distribution of odd integers along the f-triangles in the Oblong PSO.

This table is the same as the one we constructed in <https://www.mersenneforum.org/attachment.php?attachmentid=27554&stc=1&d=1667224304>,

except for the columns of even numbers, but when appropriately omitted. By observing the famous Euler sequence $x = y^2 - y + 41$ in column 21, where the difference $251 - 223 =$

28, it is evident that there are infinite offsets among odd numbers, with each aligning with another at some appropriate position in the table.

In conclusion, we can clearly observe in the verticals, as well as in all offsets with 1: *integer* slopes, the famous sequences formed by “Euler's "Lucky" numbers: n such that $m^2 - m + n$ is prime for $m = 0..n - 1$ ” cataloged in <https://oeis.org/A014556>. Additionally, these tables, along with the concepts used in [Integers are only Primals and Compounds](#) [5], allow us to study the quadratic sequences of negative primes and the use of unity as a primal, expanding Euler's initial concept with his “Lucky” numbers.

3.1 C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table

The Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table demonstrates the unique relationships between pairs of prime numbers when expressed through quadratic differences. This table provides a comprehensive overview of how integer values, represented by n , interact with a fixed value d to form prime pairs (d_1, d_2) and their corresponding mathematical operations. The table includes the following columns:

1. **Column 1 - Integer n :** This column represents the variable values of n , encompassing all integers (positive, negative, and zero). In this table, we are showing a range from -15 to 15 as an example.
2. **Column 2 - Difference $d_1 = d - n$:** This column represents the difference between a fixed value d (defined in the row where $n = 0$) and n . For a fixed d , subtract n to get d_1 .
3. **Column 3 - Sum $d_2 = d + n$:** This column represents the sum of a fixed value d (defined in the row where $n = 0$) and n . For a fixed d , add n to get d_2 .
4. **Column 4 - Product $d_1 * d_2 = (d - n)(d + n) = d^2 - n^2$ (SqMSq):** This column shows the multiplication of d_1 and d_2 , resulting in a difference of squares $d^2 - n^2$. This can also be referred to as "Square Number Minus Square Sequence" or (SqMSq) sequence. Essentially, this column represents a square number d^2 minus the sequence of square numbers n^2 <https://oeis.org/A000290>. Since $d_1 = d - n$ and $d_2 = d + n$, as we vary the value of d , all odd numbers will be multiplied with other odd numbers, and all even numbers will be multiplied with other even numbers. Consequently, an odd number will never be multiplied by an even number and vice versa.
5. **Column 5 - Partial Difference of Column 4 $dif[d_1 * d_2]$:** This column represents the difference obtained by employing the method of differences on the quadratic SqMSq column (Column 4). For any d , always results in the sequence of odd numbers <https://oeis.org/A005408>, both positive and negative.
6. **Column 6-Square Minus Product (Sq-SqMSq):** This column calculates the difference between $d^2 - d_1d_2$, resulting in n^2 <https://oeis.org/A000290> for any d .
7. **Column 7 - Difference $d_2 - d_1$:** This column represents the difference $d_2 - d_1$, which simplifies to $2n$. For any d it always results in the sequence of even numbers <https://oeis.org/A005843>, both positive and negative, including zero.

8. **Column 8 - Sum $d_1 + d_2$:** This column represents the sum $d_1 + d_2$, which simplifies to the constant $2d$ for all rows.

Additional Insights:

Since $d_1 = d - n$ and $d_2 = d + n$, there will never be operations (addition, subtraction, or multiplication) between odd and even numbers across all columns. All operations are strictly between pairs of odd numbers or even numbers.

This means that for each chosen d , there are infinite combinations of odd d_1 and d_2 pairs where the sum is $2d$. As demonstrated in the study [The Quadratic Distribution of Integers Relative to Squares and Oblongs](#) [13], there are infinite combinations of primal number pairs d_1 and d_2 for each d . Consequently, we have infinite combinations of $d_1 + d_2$ resulting in $2d$ for any d where d_1 and d_2 are primals.

The following table provides examples for d values ranging from 0 to 3:

C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table														
1	2		3		4		5		6		7		8	
n	$(d-n)(d+n) = d^2 - n^2 = \text{SqMSq}$				Odd	Sq-SqMSq	Even	$2*d$						
	d1	x	d2	=	d_1*d_2	$\text{dif}[d_1*d_2]$	$d^2 - d_1*d_2$	$d_2 - d_1$	$d_1 + d_2$					
-15	15	x	-15	=	-225	-29	225	-30	0					
-14	14	x	-14	=	-196	-27	196	-28	0					
-13	13	x	-13	=	-169	-25	169	-26	0					
-12	12	x	-12	=	-144	-23	144	-24	0					
-11	11	x	-11	=	-121	-21	121	-22	0					
-10	10	x	-10	=	-100	-19	100	-20	0					
-9	9	x	-9	=	-81	-17	81	-18	0					
-8	8	x	-8	=	-64	-15	64	-16	0					
-7	7	x	-7	=	-49	-13	49	-14	0					
-6	6	x	-6	=	-36	-11	36	-12	0					
-5	5	x	-5	=	-25	-9	25	-10	0					
-4	4	x	-4	=	-16	-7	16	-8	0					
-3	3	x	-3	=	-9	-5	9	-6	0					
-2	2	x	-2	=	-4	-3	4	-4	0					
-1	1	x	-1	=	-1	-1	1	-2	0					
0	0	x	0	=	0	1	0	0	0					
1	-1	x	1	=	-1	3	1	2	0					
2	-2	x	2	=	-4	5	4	4	0					
3	-3	x	3	=	-9	7	9	6	0					
4	-4	x	4	=	-16	9	16	8	0					
5	-5	x	5	=	-25	11	25	10	0					
6	-6	x	6	=	-36	13	36	12	0					
7	-7	x	7	=	-49	15	49	14	0					
8	-8	x	8	=	-64	17	64	16	0					
9	-9	x	9	=	-81	19	81	18	0					
10	-10	x	10	=	-100	21	100	20	0					
11	-11	x	11	=	-121	23	121	22	0					
12	-12	x	12	=	-144	25	144	24	0					
13	-13	x	13	=	-169	27	169	26	0					
14	-14	x	14	=	-196	29	196	28	0					
15	-15	x	15	=	-225		225	30	0					

Figure 9. C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table with $d = 0$

C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table														
1	2		3		4		5		6		7		8	
n	$(d-n)(d+n) = d^2 - n^2 = \text{SqMSq}$													
	d1	x	d2	=	d1*d2	diff[d1*d2]	d^2-d1*d2	d2-d1	d1+d2					
-15	16	x	-14	=	-224	-29	225	-30	2					
-14	15	x	-13	=	-195	-27	196	-28	2					
-13	14	x	-12	=	-168	-25	169	-26	2					
-12	13	x	-11	=	-143	-23	144	-24	2					
-11	12	x	-10	=	-120	-21	121	-22	2					
-10	11	x	-9	=	-99	-19	100	-20	2					
-9	10	x	-8	=	-80	-17	81	-18	2					
-8	9	x	-7	=	-63	-15	64	-16	2					
-7	8	x	-6	=	-48	-13	49	-14	2					
-6	7	x	-5	=	-35	-11	36	-12	2					
-5	6	x	-4	=	-24	-9	25	-10	2					
-4	5	x	-3	=	-15	-7	16	-8	2					
-3	4	x	-2	=	-8	-5	9	-6	2					
-2	3	x	-1	=	-3	-3	4	-4	2					
-1	2	x	0	=	0	-1	1	-2	2					
0	1	x	1	=	1	1	0	0	2					
1	0	x	2	=	0	3	1	2	2					
2	-1	x	3	=	-3	5	4	4	2					
3	-2	x	4	=	-8	7	9	6	2					
4	-3	x	5	=	-15	9	16	8	2					
5	-4	x	6	=	-24	11	25	10	2					
6	-5	x	7	=	-35	13	36	12	2					
7	-6	x	8	=	-48	15	49	14	2					
8	-7	x	9	=	-63	17	64	16	2					
9	-8	x	10	=	-80	19	81	18	2					
10	-9	x	11	=	-99	21	100	20	2					
11	-10	x	12	=	-120	23	121	22	2					
12	-11	x	13	=	-143	25	144	24	2					
13	-12	x	14	=	-168	27	169	26	2					
14	-13	x	15	=	-195	29	196	28	2					
15	-14	x	16	=	-224		225	30	2					

Figure 10. C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table with $d = 1$

C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table														
1	2		3		4		5		6		7		8	
n	$(d-n)(d+n) = d^2 - n^2 = \text{SqMSq}$													
	d1	x	d2	=	d1*d2	diff[d1*d2]	d^2-d1*d2	d2-d1	d1+d2					
-15	17	x	-13	=	-221	-29	225	-30	4					
-14	16	x	-12	=	-192	-27	196	-28	4					
-13	15	x	-11	=	-165	-25	169	-26	4					
-12	14	x	-10	=	-140	-23	144	-24	4					
-11	13	x	-9	=	-117	-21	121	-22	4					
-10	12	x	-8	=	-96	-19	100	-20	4					
-9	11	x	-7	=	-77	-17	81	-18	4					
-8	10	x	-6	=	-60	-15	64	-16	4					
-7	9	x	-5	=	-45	-13	49	-14	4					
-6	8	x	-4	=	-32	-11	36	-12	4					
-5	7	x	-3	=	-21	-9	25	-10	4					
-4	6	x	-2	=	-12	-7	16	-8	4					
-3	5	x	-1	=	-5	-5	9	-6	4					
-2	4	x	0	=	0	-3	4	-4	4					
-1	3	x	1	=	3	-1	1	-2	4					
0	2	x	2	=	4	1	0	0	4					
1	1	x	3	=	3	3	1	2	4					
2	0	x	4	=	0	5	4	4	4					
3	-1	x	5	=	-5	7	9	6	4					
4	-2	x	6	=	-12	9	16	8	4					
5	-3	x	7	=	-21	11	25	10	4					
6	-4	x	8	=	-32	13	36	12	4					
7	-5	x	9	=	-45	15	49	14	4					
8	-6	x	10	=	-60	17	64	16	4					
9	-7	x	11	=	-77	19	81	18	4					
10	-8	x	12	=	-96	21	100	20	4					
11	-9	x	13	=	-117	23	121	22	4					
12	-10	x	14	=	-140	25	144	24	4					
13	-11	x	15	=	-165	27	169	26	4					
14	-12	x	16	=	-192	29	196	28	4					
15	-13	x	17	=	-221		225	30	4					

Figure 11. C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table with $d = 2$

C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table									
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8		
n	$(d-n)(d+n) = d^2 - n^2 = \text{SqMSq}$				Odd	$\text{Sq} - \text{SqMSq}$	Even	$2*d$	
	d1	x	d2	=	$d1*d2$	$\text{dif}[d1*d2]$	$d^2 - d1*d2$	$d2 - d1$	$d1 + d2$
-15	18	x	-12	=	-216	-29	225	-30	6
-14	17	x	-11	=	-187	-27	196	-28	6
-13	16	x	-10	=	-160	-25	169	-26	6
-12	15	x	-9	=	-135	-23	144	-24	6
-11	14	x	-8	=	-112	-21	121	-22	6
-10	13	x	-7	=	-91	-19	100	-20	6
-9	12	x	-6	=	-72	-17	81	-18	6
-8	11	x	-5	=	-55	-15	64	-16	6
-7	10	x	-4	=	-40	-13	49	-14	6
-6	9	x	-3	=	-27	-11	36	-12	6
-5	8	x	-2	=	-16	-9	25	-10	6
-4	7	x	-1	=	-7	-7	16	-8	6
-3	6	x	0	=	0	-5	9	-6	6
-2	5	x	1	=	5	-3	4	-4	6
-1	4	x	2	=	8	-1	1	-2	6
0	3	x	3	=	9	1	0	0	6
1	2	x	4	=	8	3	1	2	6
2	1	x	5	=	5	5	4	4	6
3	0	x	6	=	0	7	9	6	6
4	-1	x	7	=	-7	9	16	8	6
5	-2	x	8	=	-16	11	25	10	6
6	-3	x	9	=	-27	13	36	12	6
7	-4	x	10	=	-40	15	49	14	6
8	-5	x	11	=	-55	17	64	16	6
9	-6	x	12	=	-72	19	81	18	6
10	-7	x	13	=	-91	21	100	20	6
11	-8	x	14	=	-112	23	121	22	6
12	-9	x	15	=	-135	25	144	24	6
13	-10	x	16	=	-160	27	169	26	6
14	-11	x	17	=	-187	29	196	28	6
15	-12	x	18	=	-216		225	30	6

Figure 12. C003519 Quadratic Relations of Prime Pairs Table with $d = 3$

4 Next Steps

For such a significant claim, continued validation through peer review, further empirical testing, and mathematical scrutiny in broader academic forums will be essential.

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